

A Review of Cultural Intelligence for Today's Globalised World

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ABSTRACT

Cultural intelligence, in this context, is a tool that enhances the manager's ability to interact effectively with individuals from other cultures. This study explains how cultural intelligence is essential for today's globalised world. In this review article, the researcher employed the documentary method. In the first step, reliable and valid sources were sampled randomly; in the second step, content analysis was performed on the selected papers using purposive sampling. It reveals that cultural intelligence is a relatively new concept that refers to the capacity to interact, relate, and work in diverse cultural contexts. Cultural intelligence includes knowledge of different cultures with unique histories and behaviours, applying this knowledge to one's actions, and the motivation to explore cultural differences productively. Today's workers interact with individuals from backgrounds vastly different from their daily, across various accountability levels, job roles, organisation size, and industry, in home markets and across borders. This reality necessitates a new workplace competency: the capacity to manage multiple sources of cultural diversity simultaneously. As leaders play a crucial role in ensuring that any new policy is implemented effectively and efficiently, it is essential to consider cultural intelligence in any company and not an exemption for the educational sector. A systematic review has discussed the essentials of cultural intelligence for today's globalised world in this study.

Keywords: cultural intelligence (CQ), leadership, cultural management, cross-cultural interactions, review article

INTRODUCTION

The rapid increase in cross-cultural management (CCM) because of the globalisation of economies and increased workforce mobility prompts businesses to investigate the impact of cross-cultural management on cultural intelligence. Cultural intelligence (CQ) refers to an individual's abilities and skills to manage cross-cultural interactions effectively (Eisenberg et al., 2013). Underscoring the significance of cross-border effectiveness in today's globalised world, cultural intelligence is related to the leadership capacity to manage effectively in culturally diverse contexts. It is a crucial leadership competency for those with cross-border responsibilities (Rockstuhl et al., 2011). Given the significance of foreign social networks and the interconnectedness of global business transactions, academics have argued that entrepreneurs' cultural knowledge and skills are crucial factors in determining the quality of

their relationships with foreign networks. Considering the impact of culture, entrepreneurs' cultural intelligence (CQ) is a critical factor that improves relationship quality (Charoensukmongkol, 2015). Therefore, multinational corporations depend on their teams' creativity, productivity, etc., to compete in uncertain and cutthroat business environments. International corporations have the option to share the knowledge of teams from various countries. They can acquire, utilise, and expand this knowledge. As a result, most workplaces provide access to mass cultures. Many new challenges, such as managing cultural diversity, have emerged due to globalisation for individuals and businesses. Sharing one's knowledge can improve both individual and team performance. Diverse workforces could contribute to the addition of knowledge resources in dynamic organisations. Very few studies have been conducted on the new concept of cultural intelligence. Therefore, the new concept of cultural intelligence in today's globalised world is essential to review.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Globalisation and Cultural Intelligence (CQ)

Globalisation and the liberalisation of trade and services in many regions of the world have made it possible for multinational corporations to operate in diverse geographical settings. In this regard, the effectiveness of international assignments is becoming a significant source of competitive advantage for many businesses. Establishing new global markets, disseminating, sustaining corporate culture, facilitating organisational coordination control, and transferring technology, knowledge, and skills benefit companies that send employees abroad (Rose et al., 2010). Globalisation has enabled businesses to operate internationally and capitalise on global talent pools. Effective global leadership is required to manage a culturally diverse workforce in this new environment. Cultural intelligence (CQ) and openness are essential to effective global leadership. Global leaders with these characteristics will be more effective in international organisations (Verghese & D'Netto, 2011). Practitioners of Human Resource Management (HRM) have long recognised how crucial it is for managers, especially senior ones, to be able to navigate the national and organisational cultural contexts in which they operate. Regarding expatriates, for instance, a great deal of focus has been placed on selecting and training individuals to work in foreign cultures. The commonly held belief that national cultural differences are becoming less significant due to globalisation, this paper argues that understanding cultures is becoming increasingly important (Stening, 2006). Globalisation has made business a problematic endeavour. Additionally, it has resulted in forming multicultural organisations in which individuals from various cultures work under one roof. Organisations require a new generation of culturally sensitive managers to manage a diverse workforce. In this context, cultural intelligence is a tool that enhances the manager's ability to interact effectively with individuals from other cultures (Jyoti et al., 2015). There is a correlation between cultural intelligence, expatriate adaptation to the host country's culture, and expatriate performance on international assignments. The focus is on the direct impact of expatriates' cultural intelligence on general, social, and occupational adjustments. The improved adjustments have consequently positive effects on the expatriates' task and contextual performance. Researchers in international human resource management (IHRM) managers are impacted by these implications (Malek & Budhwar, 2013). Therefore, cultural intelligence is essential for human resource management, especially global businesses.

The Essential of Cultural Intelligence (CQ)

Everyone does not possess the ability to interact effectively across multiple cultures; however, it is becoming increasingly essential in today's global business environment. This

skill has recently been labelled cultural intelligence (CQ) and has attracted the attention of business leaders and academics (Crowne, 2008). Cultural intelligence (CQ) is the ability to function effectively in intercultural settings. It has attracted growing attention from researchers and practitioners due to its contemporary relevance to globalisation, international management, and workforce diversity. According to current research, CQ predicts various crucial outcomes in intercultural contexts, including cultural adaptation, expatriate performance, global leadership, intercultural negotiation, and multicultural team processes (Van Dyne et al., 2012). Even though scholars and practitioners have repeatedly emphasised the importance of intercultural negotiation, surprisingly, little research has examined the factors that predict intercultural negotiation success. There is the influence of cultural intelligence (CQ) on intercultural negotiation processes and outcomes while controlling for other types of intelligence (cognitive ability and emotional intelligence), personality (openness and extraversion), and international experience (Imai & Gelfand, 2010). Therefore, cultural intelligence (CQ) can refer to an individual's, a team's, or a company's capabilities. Cultural intelligence is essential for most individuals and organisations due to the world's diversity and the fact that modern organisations recognise the importance of bridging cultures for individual and organisational success (Van Dyne et al., 2019). Cultural intelligence is the ability to interact with culturally diverse individuals effectively. Cultural intelligence is distinctive due to the ability to generate appropriate behaviour in a new cultural setting (Thomas, 2006).

The Key Elements of Cultural Intelligence (CQ)

In today's globalised economy, success in a particular industry almost necessitates a global perspective on conducting business. Limiting one's economic activities to the domestic market will ultimately result in disadvantages compared to multinational corporations capable of rapid expansion in emerging markets. The digital transformation has become the enabler to serving global customers and increasing the business's responsiveness in all areas, thereby expanding the opportunities for companies that operate across national boundaries. At the same time, this fact increases the pressure on companies that are driving hypercompetition on a global scale. Companies must internationalise their businesses to survive in this globalised, hypercompetitive world (Rüth & Netzer, 2020). Over the past few decades, many professionals have been tasked with rethinking the fundamental paradigms of leadership styles and how to achieve success in this global era. A culturally competent leader is not desirable but a requirement in virtually all organisations. The relationship between leadership styles and four components of cultural intelligence was confirmed to shed light on this complex leadership adaptation in multi-cultural environments. Aside from the correlation between democratic leadership style and cultural intelligence motivation, this study found no other correlations between leadership styles and cultural intelligence (Eken et al., 2014). Cultural intelligence (CQ) is a multidimensional construct of four fundamental "intelligence": metacognitive, cognitive, motivational, and behavioural. Meta-cognitive cultural intelligence reflects a person's cultural awareness during interactions with people from diverse backgrounds. Cognitive CQ relates to a person's knowledge of specific norms, practices, and conventions in new cultural settings. Motivational CQ encapsulates a person's desire to learn and function effectively in diverse cultural contexts. Lastly, Behavioral CQ is conceptualised as an individual's adaptability in demonstrating culturally appropriate behaviour when interacting with individuals from various cultural backgrounds (Ward et al., 2011). Thus, cultural intelligence is a multidimensional construct of intelligence, such as metacognitive, cognitive, motivational, and behavioural cultural intelligence.

The Essential of Cultural Intelligence (CQ) in Education

Lack of understanding of the roles of cultural distance and prior international experience in CQ development may prevent universities and individuals from maximising the educational and developmental potential of short-term study abroad. As a result of ignoring critical boundary conditions, incorrect participant selection decisions could be made, less efficient programmes could be designed, and more remote, more expensive locations could be selected, resulting in less desirable outcomes (Iskhakova et al., 2022). Cultural intelligence (CQ) is a tool that can enhance a person's ability to interact with individuals from other cultures. School leaders' perceptions regarding the critical influences of cultural intelligence on their leadership style adaptability are essential (Aldhaferi, 2017). Cross-cultural selling has become an integral component of sales training. Students who enter the workforce in frontline customer service positions are expected to perform sales at a higher level in the current competitive business graduate job market. It has been discovered that undergraduate students who acquire a sales education have a more realistic view of sales as a profession, require minimal training, have lower turnover, and need less time to be more productive. This has been attributed to the success of college-level sales education curricula and sales education techniques (Delpechitre & Baker, 2017). In addition, there has been an absence of interdisciplinary exchange between the best science and practices of intercultural competence from other fields and the field of citizenship education. Cultural intelligence, a theory-based and empirically rigorous concept, provides the optimal framework for promoting intercultural competence in character and citizenship education. Therefore, teachers face the opportunity and challenge of leading and teaching with cultural intelligence. Intercultural competence is an unavoidable component of nature and citizenship education. There is a relationship between the theory and practice of cultural intelligence and citizenship education. It provides examples of how teachers can teach with cultural intelligence and cultivate culturally intelligent students who will become multiculturally educated and globally engaged citizens (Goh, 2012). Thus, academic discussions on cultural intelligence (CQ) are now focusing on their various potential applications. In addition to business administration, the field of study is expanded to include psychology, education, tourism, communication, and the arts. This results from the widespread breakdown of global communication competence in multicultural settings due to globalisation's intensification (Hong et al., 2021)

METHODOLOGY

Researchers must utilise their knowledge to select the most beneficial sample for their research. In qualitative research, this method is frequently employed. The purpose is to acquire comprehensive knowledge. The texts are a typical point of departure for qualitative content analysis. The objective is to condense a large volume of text into a highly organised and concise summary of key findings (Limna et al., 2022 Jaipong et al., 2022). In this review, the researcher employed the documentary method. In the first step, reliable and valid sources were sampled randomly; in the second step, content analysis was performed on the selected papers using purposive sampling. This systematic review utilised five databases, including EBSCO, Google Scholar, Scopus, Web of Science, and ScienceDirect. In addition, the criteria for inclusion included studies that 1) clearly related to cultural intelligence, 2) were published in English, and 3) were peer-reviewed. The secondary data were examined between July 15 and August 25, 2022. The articles were searched on the keywords terms to search the database as follows; Cultural intelligence (CQ), leadership, cultural management, cross-cultural interactions, and review article. Twenty-four articles (24) out of 8,320 results were analysed using content analysis. The research articles were from the year 2006-2022.

RESULTS

The rapid growth of cross-cultural management due to the globalisation of economies and the increased workforce mobility compels businesses to investigate the impact of CCM on cultural intelligence. Cultural intelligence (CQ) refers to the abilities and skills of an individual to effectively manage cross-cultural interactions. It is argued that cultural intelligence is related to the leadership capacity to work effectively in culturally diverse contexts, highlighting the importance of cross-border effectiveness in today's globalised world. It is an essential leadership skill for those with international responsibilities. Given the significance of foreign social networks and the interconnectedness of global business transactions, academics have asserted that entrepreneurs' cultural knowledge and skills are crucial determinants of their relationships with foreign networks. Considering the impact of culture, entrepreneurs' cultural intelligence (CQ) is crucial in enhancing the quality of their relationships. Therefore, multinational corporations rely on their teams' creativity, efficiency, etc. to compete in uncertain and cutthroat business environments. Globalisation and the liberalisation of trade and services in numerous regions have enabled multinational corporations to operate in various geographical settings. In this regard, the efficacy of international assignments is becoming an increasingly important source of competitive advantage for many businesses. Establishing new global markets, disseminating, sustaining corporate culture, facilitating organisational coordination and control, and transferring technology, knowledge, and skills are advantages for companies that send workers overseas. Globalisation has enabled businesses to operate internationally and profit from global talent pools. Effective global leadership is required to manage a culturally diverse workforce in this new environment. Cultural intelligence (CQ) and openness are crucial to global leadership effectiveness. Practitioners of Human Resource Management (HRM) have long acknowledged how important it is for managers, particularly senior ones, to be able to navigate the national and organisational cultural contexts in which they operate. A substantial emphasis has been placed on selecting and preparing individuals to work in foreign cultures. Contrary to the commonly held belief that globalisation is diminishing the significance of national cultural differences, understanding cultures is becoming increasingly important. Globalisation has rendered business problematic. In addition, it has led to the formation of multicultural organisations in which people from various cultures work together. Organisations require a new generation of culturally sensitive managers to manage a diverse workforce. The leaders with these traits will be more effective in international organisations.

CONCLUSIONS

Cultural intelligence (CQ) is a multidimensional concept comprised of four fundamental "intelligence": metacognitive, cognitive, motivational, and behavioural. Meta-cognitive cultural intelligence reflects a person's cultural sensitivity during interactions with individuals from various backgrounds. In contrast, Cognitive CQ refers to a person's familiarity with norms, practices, and conventions in unfamiliar cultural contexts. Motivational CQ encapsulates an individual's desire to learn and effectively function in diverse cultural contexts. Lastly, Behavioral CQ is conceptualised as an individual's adaptability to demonstrate culturally appropriate behaviour when interacting with people of different cultures. Thus, cultural intelligence is a multidimensional construct consisting of metacognitive, cognitive, motivational, and behavioural cultural intelligence. Companies must internationalise their operations to survive today's globalised, hypercompetitive

environment. Many professionals have been tasked with rethinking the fundamental paradigms of leadership styles and how to achieve success in this global era over the past few decades. In virtually all organisations, cultural competence is not a desirable trait but rather a requirement. There is a relationship between leadership styles and four components of cultural intelligence to shed light on this complex adaptation of leadership in multi-cultural environments. This study found no other correlations between leadership styles and cultural intelligence besides the correlation between democratic leadership style and cultural intelligence motivation. Cross-cultural selling is now an integral part of sales education. In the current competitive business graduate job market, it is expected that students who enter the workforce in customer service positions will perform sales at a higher level. It has been discovered that undergraduates with a sales education have a more realistic view of sales as a profession, require minimal training, have lower turnover rates, and need less time to be more productive. This results from the success of college-level sales education curricula and sales education techniques. In addition, there has been a lack of inter-disciplinary exchange between the best intercultural competence science and practices from other fields and the field of citizenship education. The optimal framework for promoting intercultural competence in character and citizenship education is cultural intelligence, a concept grounded in theory and supported by empirical evidence. In addition to business administration, the field of study now encompasses psychology, education, tourism, communication, and the arts. Due to the intensification of globalisation, this is the result of extensive research into global communication proficiency in multicultural settings.

LIMITATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

It would be deceptive to ignore the limitations of scoping studies. They do not evaluate the quality of evidence in primary research reports, for instance, formally. The amount of data generated can be substantial. It can lead to difficult decisions regarding how breadth (covering all available material) trumps depth. The scoping study does not address the synthesis issue or the relative weight of evidence supporting the efficacy of any intervention. Consequently, scoping studies provide a narrative or descriptive summary of the available research. Most of these challenges are addressed by systematic review methods that require quality assessment, thereby reducing the number of studies included in the review and emphasising data synthesis. However, the systematic review process can be very time-consuming, which is a disadvantage when policymakers need information about existing research evidence quickly. The recommendation for further study is to consider quantitative for relationship explanation or qualitative research such as interviews and focus group discussions for insight results.

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